

PECULIARITIES OF THE AGRICULTURAL ECONOMY IN THE COUNTRIES OF THE EUROPEAN UNION.

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Abstract.

This article presents a number of information about the organization, management and specific aspects of agriculture in the European Union countries.

Key words.

Agricultural products, European Union, benefits, financial indicators, agricultural economy, farming practice.

Agricultural products, food and culinary traditions are a key part of the regional and cultural identity of the European Union (EU). This is due, at least in part, to the different natural environments, climates and farming practices that feed a wide range of agricultural products. Almost two-fifths of the land of the European Union (38.2%) is occupied by agricultural products.

Farmers in the EU are increasingly encouraged to manage their countryside as a public domain for the benefit of society as a whole.

The EU is stepping up its efforts to encourage young people to start farming by helping them set up their own businesses through benefits such as start-up grants, income support and further training . According to the data of 2022, the heads of farms in three out of five regions of the European Union are young, qualified managers.

On 2 December, 2021, the agreement on reform of the common agricultural policy (CAP) was formally adopted. The new legislation, which entered into force on 1 January 2023, paves the way for a fairer, greener and more performance-based CAP.

It seeks to ensure a sustainable future for European farmers, provide more targeted support to smaller farms, and allow greater flexibility for EU countries to adapt measures to local conditions. Agriculture and rural areas are central to

the European Green Deal, and the CAP 2023-27 will be a key tool in reaching the ambitions of the Farm to Fork and biodiversity strategies.¹⁸⁷

Sources of agricultural financing in the European Union¹⁸⁸

Austria's Salzburg region has the highest share of young farm managers (under 35 years of age) among all regions (15,7%). And in Portugal, there are four regional agrocluster areas where more than half of the farm managers are aged 65 and over.

According to 2022 data, there were 10,3 million farms in the European Union and they used 157 million hectares of land. The number of labor force employed in the agricultural sector of the European Union is 20,0 million people. As of January 1, 2022, the population of the European Union was 446,8 million, which is 172 000 less than the previous year. The European Union covers an area of more than 4 million km² and has a population of 447,7 million.

1-table.

Financial indicators of the countries of the European Union

Indicators	2021 year	2022 year
Total population of the European Union, million people	446,972	446,8
Including the population employed in agriculture	20,7	20,0

¹⁸⁷ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27_en

¹⁸⁸ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/agri-statistical-factsheet-eu_en_0.pdf

Total land area of the European Union. million people	4 million km ²	4 million km ²
The amount of land occupied in agriculture	157 million hectares	157 million hectares
GDP volume of the European Union, euro	14,45 trillion	16,6 trillion
The share of agricultural sectors, EUR	177,12 billion	222,3 billion
Share of total GDP	12,25%	14 %
The GDP of the country with the highest share in the GDP of the European Union, euro	Germaniya; 4 230 172 billion	Germaniya; 4 268 144 billion

Contribution of EU countries to the total agricultural output. (as of 2021-2022)

It can be seen from the above diagram that France-19%, Italy-13,9% and Estonia-13,7% are the top countries in the supply of agricultural products among the EU countries.

The economic importance of agriculture was relatively low in most capital regions of the EU, where land is at a premium and service industries tend to predominate; this reflects, at least to some degree, the administrative boundaries that are used to demarcate regions. In the capital regions of Germany, Hungary, Austria and Sweden, gross value added from agriculture accounted for less than

0,1 % of economic activity in 2019; this was also the case for the German region of Bremen¹⁸⁹.

The specific features of the agricultural economy in the European Union are as follows:

1. Availability of government programs to double world food production by 2050 to ensure population growth and development of food habits;

2. The EU will financially support its farmers and encourage sustainable and environmentally friendly practices, while investing in the development of rural areas;

3. EU institutions cooperate in the development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of food and farming policy. Implementation of laws agreed at the EU level by national and local authorities;

4. Provision of funds through the EU budget to member states for the development of agricultural sectors in accordance with the rules set at the EU level;

5. Agriculture and food-related industries and services provide more than 44 million jobs in the EU, including 20 million people in agriculture alone.

6. The European Union is one of the world's leading producers and exporters of agricultural products, thanks to its diverse climate, fertile soils, farmers' technical skills and product quality.

7. The Common Agricultural Policy of the European Union is a partnership between society and agriculture that ensures a sustainable food supply, protects farmers' incomes, protects the environment and revitalizes rural areas.

2-table.

Based on the above information, we conducted a SWOT analysis of the agricultural economy of the European Union countries.

<p>Strengths Of the possibilities of fauna and flora. High tourist attraction and potential. Competitive agriculture. Availability resources for agriculture and forestry.</p>	<p>Weaknesses Poor development of agricultural economic structures. Poor communication networks. Discrimination against foreigners.</p>
<p>Opportunities Potential for value addition in agriculture, forestry, biomass, tourism, biotechnology. Attractive location for secondary</p>	<p>Threats Migration and economic development of commuting regions prevents. Population decline and low birth rates</p>

¹⁸⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/15234730/15242104/KS-HA-22-001-EN-N.pdf/ffb89e8c-a7c9-517e-101f-13462ba1cf65>

residence. Benefits provided by the state.	increase the demand for labor
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REFERENCES:

1. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/15234730/15242104/KS-HA-22-001-EN-N.pdf/ffb89e8c-a7c9-517e-101f-13462ba1cf65>
1. <https://www.google.com/search?client=opera&q=The+volume+of+GDP+of+the+European+Union%2C+2021&sourceid=opera&ie=UTF-8&oe=UTF-8>
2. <https://www.google.com/search?client=opera&q=The+size+of+the+GDP+of+the+European+Union+in+2022&sourceid=opera&ie=UTF-8&oe=UTF-8>
3. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/agri-statistical-factsheet-eu_en_0.pdf
4. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy_en
5. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>
6. https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/estat_regio/items/topic/12249
7. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/SWOT-анализ>
8. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/SWOTanalysis-for-rural-areas-and-economy_tbl3_233486629